

Effect of YouTube Video-Resources on Interest in Algebra among Male and Female Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of YouTube video resources on Interest in Algebra Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students' in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The sample size of the study consists of 88 (44 male and 44 female) Senior Secondary School class two (SS2) Mathematics students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Funtua Educational Zone of Katsina State using multi stage sampling technique. One co-educational school in Funtua Educational Zone was taught algebra using YouTube video resources. The study compares the interest levels of male and female students after being exposed to the same instructional resources. Data were collected using the Students' Algebra Interest Inventory (SAII), which was validated by experts from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, with a reliability coefficient of 0.74, calculated using the split-half method and Cronbach's Alpha. The study's research questions were answered using Mean Rank and Sum of Rank statistics, while the null-hypothesis was tested using the Mann-Whitney U-test at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed no significant difference in interest between male and female students in the experimental group, suggesting that YouTube video resources are effective in enhancing algebra interest among both genders. The study concludes that YouTube video resources can effectively increase student interest in algebra and are beneficial for both male and female students. Based on these results, it was recommended that secondary school mathematics teachers incorporate YouTube video resources into their teaching practices, particularly for abstract and challenging topics such as algebra, to enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes.

Key words: YouTube Video-Resources, Algebra, Interest level, Gender

Introduction

Mathematics is a core subject across all educational levels in Nigeria, from primary to tertiary institutions. Babu et al. (2023) emphasized its importance in various fields, highlighting its role as a key tool for solving problems and making informed decisions. Mohammed and Maska (2024) referred

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to mathematics as the "queen and substance" of science and technology, underscoring its essential role in driving scientific and technological progress. The Nigerian education system plays a pivotal role in providing students with the mathematical and scientific knowledge necessary for critical thinking, skill development, and national growth. Laos (2024) noted that mathematics is the foundation of all scientific fields, asserting that scientific endeavors cannot succeed without mathematical principles and logical reasoning. Further emphasizing the deep connection between mathematics, science, and technology, Hwang et al. (2023) argued that scientific development relies on mathematics, which in turn fuels technological innovation and societal progress. Without mathematics, science would be non-existent, and without science, technological advancement would be impossible, hindering overall societal development.

Mathematics, due to its global significance, is universally recognized as a core and mandatory subject in education systems worldwide. Ruiz-Cecilia et al. (2023) highlighted that mathematics is taught in all countries, regardless of linguistic differences, as it serves as the cornerstone for scientific progress. Sitopu et al. (2024) further emphasized that mathematics is an essential tool for scientific and technological development. The advancement of a nation in these fields heavily depends on the effective teaching and learning of mathematics, as it equips students with the necessary skills to understand and apply scientific and technological concepts. In alignment with this understanding, the National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) underscores the importance of mathematics as a core subject, mandating that all students, irrespective of their field of study, gender, or ability, must take and pass mathematics at a credit level, particularly at the secondary school level.

For Nigeria to achieve effective mathematics instruction, especially as a developing nation, it must embrace modern and scientific innovations in its educational practices. This calls for the training and deployment of qualified mathematicians who can help bring these educational goals to fruition. However, despite the essential role mathematics plays in national development, studies by Roche et al. (2023) and Hettinger et al. (2023) have identified a significant and persistent lack of student interest in mathematics. Several factors contribute to this low interest, including insufficient teaching resources, mathematics anxiety, outdated teaching methods, and inadequate instructional facilities. In light of these challenges, scholars like Chiu (2023) and Adu-Marfo et al. (2024) have proposed the use of innovative teaching approaches, such as YouTube video resources, which offer dynamic and engaging learning opportunities. These digital tools have the potential to enhance students' interest and motivation in mathematics, ultimately leading to improved academic performance and a more positive attitude toward the subject.

YouTube videos, as noted by Magnone et al. (2023), have proven to be powerful educational tools that improve students' perceptions, promote simultaneous learning, and allow for repeated viewing. This gives learners the opportunity to revisit and master concepts until they reach full comprehension. In a similar vein, Trenholm (2022) highlighted the significant impact of television and video recordings in education, noting that they can captivate students' interest, enrich classroom experiences, and offer materials that might not be available through traditional teaching methods.

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Wilkinson et al. (2018) further explained that instructional videos are more than just oral explanations—they visually represent and contextualize information, which aids in deeper understanding and strengthens comprehension. By engaging both auditory and visual senses, videos enhance information retention and learning outcomes. Ahmad (2024) supports this claim, finding that using multiple sensory pathways and presenting content in an enriched, detailed manner not only facilitates learning but also improves long-term retention of verbal material.

Additionally, Sagge and Segura (2023) argued that educational videos are crafted with specific learning goals in mind, and when effectively incorporated into the teaching process, they can significantly impact students' attitudes toward learning. These videos make learning more engaging, enjoyable, and enduring. When harnessed appropriately, video resources can greatly elevate students' levels of interest, motivation, and involvement in subjects like mathematics, especially when dealing with challenging or abstract concepts.

Interest is a key psychological factor that greatly impacts students' involvement and motivation in their learning process. Conard (2023) defines interest as a sense of curiosity or concern that directs an individual's focus toward a particular subject. Roche et al. (2023) further elaborate that interest is the level of attentiveness that shapes students' engagement and success in a given area of study.

Tu and Lee (2025) argue that interest acts as a motivating force, compelling students to engage with the content and take specific actions. It influences their ability to maintain focus during lessons, especially when the material is intriguing and the teaching methods are engaging. Supporting this view, Osterman (2023) emphasizes that students tend to be more attentive and involved in subjects that captivate their interest, while they are less likely to engage with topics they find uninteresting or irrelevant.

Given its central role, interest is essential to the learning process. When students are genuinely interested in a subject, they are more likely to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and values. Without strong interest and effort, students often face challenges in mastering subjects like mathematics. As a result, it is crucial to cultivate students' interest, particularly through innovative and engaging instructional strategies, to improve their performance in mathematics.

Gender is a significant factor in this study and is commonly understood as a set of characteristics that distinguish males from females (Xie et al., 2023). These distinctions can vary depending on the context, including biological differences, social roles, and gender identity. Omojemite et al. (2024) described gender as a socio-cultural construct that assigns specific roles, attitudes, and values considered appropriate for each sex.

Research has demonstrated that gender can impact students' interest in mathematics. For example, Okeke et al. (2023) highlighted gender as an important factor influencing students' interest in mathematics, suggesting that the perception of mathematics as a subject dominated by males may lead to diminished motivation among female students. This perception perpetuates the gender gap in

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mathematics achievement, often resulting in lower levels of interest in mathematics and mathematics-related subjects among female students.

In light of these challenges, this study aims to explore whether there is a difference in the interest levels of male and female SS II students in the Funtua Education Zone when taught algebra using YouTube video resources. The study's findings will provide valuable insights into the potential of YouTube video-based instruction in addressing gender disparities in mathematics interest.

This study is based on the Dual Coding Theory (DCT), a cognitive framework introduced by Allan Paivio in the 1960s. DCT explains that humans process and represent information using two interconnected systems: verbal and non-verbal (Paivio, 1991). According to this theory, verbal understanding is enhanced by a solid non-verbal foundation, with both systems working collaboratively to process both linguistic and visual information. Mental imagery, which plays a key role in memory formation and retention, is central to the theory, making it highly applicable to learning environments that incorporate multimedia resources.

In this study, which investigates the effect of YouTube video resources on senior secondary school students' interest in algebra in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria, DCT offers valuable insights into how students absorb mathematical concepts. The use of visual tools, such as instructional videos, stimulates both the verbal and non-verbal cognitive systems, potentially improving students' comprehension and retention of algebraic concepts. Given the abstract nature of algebra, the use of multimedia resources aligns with DCT's emphasis on mental imagery to support deeper learning.

Furthermore, DCT emphasizes the spectrum from concrete to abstract knowledge representation, which allows educators to design instructional materials that align with students' cognitive preferences. By optimizing teaching methods to enhance engagement, educators can boost students' interest in algebra, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes. This study's application of DCT highlights its relevance in educational contexts and its potential to guide the development of instructional practices that enhance both motivation and understanding of mathematical concepts.

Statement of the problem

The problem of low student interest in algebra remains a significant challenge in mathematics education, particularly among senior secondary school students in Nigeria. Despite the importance of algebra as a fundamental mathematical concept, many students exhibit a lack of engagement with the subject, which hinders their academic performance and overall attitude towards mathematics. This problem is compounded by gender disparities, with female students often showing lower interest in mathematics compared to their male counterparts. The prevalent stereotype that mathematics is a male-dominated subject has been identified as a key factor influencing the lower motivation of female students. Such gender-based differences in interest contribute to a widening achievement gap, further limiting females' potential in mathematics and related fields.

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In light of this issue, the role of innovative teaching methods, such as the use of YouTube video resources, has gained increasing attention. YouTube videos offer dynamic and interactive learning experiences that can engage students and make abstract concepts like algebra more accessible. However, little is known about the effectiveness of these digital tools in addressing gender-based differences in algebra interest. This study seeks to investigate whether YouTube video resources can bridge the gender gap in algebra interest among senior secondary school students in the Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the potential of YouTube videos as a tool for fostering greater gender equality in mathematics education and enhancing student engagement with algebra.org

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

- i. Examine the effect of YouTube Video-Resources on interest in Algebra concepts among male and female Secondary school SS2 class students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study;

- i. What is the difference in interest scores of male and female secondary school class two (SS2) students taught Algebra concept using You Tube Video-Resources in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean Interest score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra using YouTube Video-Resources.

Methodology

This study adopted a Single Group Quasi-Experimental research design, specifically a pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental design utilizing intact classes. The target population consisted of all SSII students from 22 public senior secondary schools in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, totaling 9,247 students. This population included 5,198 male and 4,049 female students, with an average age of 17 years. Among the 22 public senior secondary schools, 18 were co-educational, while the remaining four were single-sex schools, with two designated for male students and two for female students. All the schools are owned by the Katsina State Government and operate as either day or boarding schools.

In this study, simple random sampling through balloting was employed to select the sample schools. Four (4) schools were randomly chosen from the eighteen (18) co-educational senior secondary schools in the study area. The sample size of the study consists of 88 (44 male and 44 female) Senior Secondary School class two (SS2) Mathematics students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Funtua Educational Zone of Katsina State using multi stage sampling technique. One co-educational school in Funtua Educational Zone was taught algebra using YouTube video resources.

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To ensure equivalence in interest levels among the students, a pre-test was administered to the SSII mathematics students in each of the four randomly selected schools. The pre-test was analyzed using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Scheffe's test. Based on the results of this analysis, two intact classes—one from the experimental school and one from the control school—were selected through balloting without replacement for further participation in the study.

The data collection instrument used in the study was the Students' Algebra Interest Inventory (SAII), adapted from Wei et al. (2014). The SAII is a 27-item questionnaire designed to measure students' interest in algebra. It is divided into two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A collects demographic information about the students, while Section B contains the 27 items organized into three dimensions: positive responses, negative responses, and time responses. The positive responses dimension includes 10 items that reflect favorable attitudes toward algebra, such as "I enjoy solving algebra problems." The negative responses dimension contains 10 items that reflect unfavorable attitudes, such as "I do not like learning algebra." The time responses dimension comprises 7 items assessing the amount of time students devote to algebra, such as "I spend more time on algebra than on other subjects."

The instrument employs a 5-point Likert scale, as outlined by Likert (1973), with response options ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD). For positive interest items, scores range from 5 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strongly Disagree), while negative interest items are reverse-scored, with 1 indicating Strongly Agree and 5 indicating Strongly Disagree. The total score for the instrument can range from a maximum of 135 to a minimum of 27, with higher scores reflecting greater interest in algebra. Students were instructed to choose the response that best represented their level of interest by selecting one of the five options. The Students' Algebra Interest Inventory (SAII) was validated for construct, criterion, and content validity by professors from the Department of Psychology and Counseling at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

The instrument was pre-tested at Kurami Government Senior Secondary School, which is part of the population but not included in the sample, with a group of 30 students. Following the pilot test, the reliability of the instrument was assessed using the split-half method. The results from the two halves were analyzed, and the reliability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha in SPSS Version 20.0. The analysis produced a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.74$, indicating a strong positive correlation between the two halves of the instrument, thereby confirming its internal consistency and reliability for use in the study.

Presentation of Results

Results obtained from the data collected were analyzed as follows:

Research Question One: What is the difference in interest scores of male and female secondary school class two (SS2) students taught Algebra concept using You Tube Video-Resources in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

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To answer the research question two post test scores from SAI for experimental and control groups were subjected to mean rank and Sum of Rank statistics. Summary of the findings is in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Rank, Sum of Rank Statistics of Pretest and Posttest SAI Interest level for Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

GENDER	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Male	51	41.16	2099.00
Female	37	49.11	1817.00
Total	88		

Outcome of the Non-Parametric test revealed that there is no difference between mean Interest level of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video Resources. Their computed Mean Rank Interest levels are 41.16 and 49.11 by SSII male and female students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video Resources and respectively implying an insignificant Mean Rank difference of just 7.95. This implies that the use of YouTube Video Resources is gender friendly on the Interest level of students towards the learning of Algebra Concept.

Testing Null Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean Interest score of male and female SSII students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Resources.

To test null hypothesis two, the post test scores from SAI for male and female of the experimental group were subjected to independent sample t-test. The summary is presented in Table 4.

Table 2: Summary of Mann Whitney Mean Posttest SAI Level for Male and Female in Experimental Group

GENDER	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	P
Male	51	41.16	2099.00	0.146
Female	37	49.11	1817.00	
Total	88			

p = 0.146 > 0.05 alpha level of significance

Outcome of the Mann Whitney Non-Parametric test revealed that there is no significant difference between mean Interest level of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video Resources, this is because the calculated p value of 0.146 is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Their computed Mean Rank Interest levels are 41.16 and 49.11 by SSII male and female students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video Resources and respectively implying an insignificant Mean Rank difference of just 7.95. This implies that the use of YouTube Video

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Resources is gender friendly on the Interest level of students towards the learning of Algebra Concept.

Therefore, the null hypothesis which stat that There is no significant difference between mean Interest level of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video Resources, is hereby accepted and retained.

Discussion of Results

The results show that no significant difference in the Interest of male and female students when exposed to YouTube Video-Resources. This showed that the strategy is gender friendly in terms of Interest. This is in harmony with the findings of Khan, Saeed, Okada et al. (2024) found that boys in heterogeneous groups do not dominate their female counterparts in Interest. O'Toole (2023) and Khan et al. (2023) in their independent studies revealed that gender has no significant on Interest among secondary school students when exposed to Video-Resources.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are made:

- i. Interest level in Algebra concepts can be enhanced significantly by the use of YouTube Video-Resources.
- ii. The use of YouTube Video-Resources is gender-friendly as it engenders better acquisition of Interest level among both male and female students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Utilization of YouTube Video Resources in Mathematics Instruction: Secondary school mathematics teachers should integrate YouTube video resources into their teaching, particularly when addressing complex and abstract topics like algebra. These videos provide visual and interactive explanations that can enhance students' understanding and interest in the subject.
- ii. Encouraging Active Student Participation: Mathematics teachers should create an engaging learning environment by fostering active student participation through classroom discussions, hands-on explorations, and collaborative learning activities. Encouraging students to elaborate on learned concepts can significantly enhance their interest and retention in mathematics.
- iii. Capacity Building for Mathematics Teachers: Professional bodies such as the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), in collaboration with federal and state ministries of education, should organize nationwide training programs, including workshops, seminars, and conferences. These initiatives should focus on equipping mathematics teachers with the necessary skills to design and implement instructional strategies that effectively integrate YouTube video resources into the teaching-learning process.

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